

Why does the Big Dipper rotate with the seasons

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Abstract

The observed direction of the Big Dipper changes with the seasons although the Big Dipper is the seven fixed stars in the constellation Ursa Major. The model of the earth's rotation and revolution around the sun well explains the sunrise, sunset and the changes in the four seasons. However, this model cannot explain why the direction of the Big Dipper changes with the seasons. In order to solve this problem, I take the earth as the origin of reference system to observe the sun and the planets in the solar system. The observation results in the new reference system can not only explain the changes of sunrise, sunset and the four seasons, but also reasonably explain the changes in the directions of the Big Dipper with the four seasons.

Key Words: Relative Motion, Earth, Sun, Planets, Ursa Major

As long ago as 340 B.C. the Greek philosopher Aristotle thought that the earth was stationary and that the sun, the moon, the planets, and the stars moved in circular orbits around the earth. This idea was elaborated by Ptolemy in the second century A.D. into a complete cosmological model. After more than a thousand year, a different model was proposed in 1514 by a Polish, Nicholas Copernicus[1]. His idea was that the sun was stationary at the center, and that the earth and the planets moved in circular orbits around the sun. Nearly a century passed before Copernicus' idea was taken seriously. Until 1609, the Italian, Galileo Galilei found that, with a telescope, the planet Jupiter was accompanied by several small satellites that orbited around it. This implied that everything did not have to orbit directly around the earth, as Aristotle and Ptolemy had thought. An explanation was provided much later, in 1687, when Sir Isaac Newton published his *Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica*[2]. Newton postulated a law of universal gravitation according to which each body in the universe was attracted toward every other body by a force that was stronger the more massive the bodies and the closer they were to each other. Newton went on to show that, according to his law, gravity causes the moon to move in an elliptical orbit around the earth, and causes the earth and the planets to follow elliptical

paths around the sun. By then, the heliocentric model had been perfected. Although Einstein's general theory of relativity predicted a slightly different motion from Newton's theory[3], it has been universally accepted that the earth travels around the sun in an elliptical orbit for more than four centuries.

The details of the heliocentric model are that, as shown in Fig. 1, the earth revolves continuously around its axis SN once a day and around the sun once a year. With this model the situations can be perfectly explained that the sun rises in the East and sets in the West, and that there is four seasons, spring, summer, autumn, and winter, in one year (Fig. 1(a)).

Figure 1. Heliocentric model, (a) the earth revolves continuously around its axis SN once a day and around the sun once a year, (b) When the earth travels around the sun the direction of its axis SN keep unchanged and points to the Polaris.

However, the observed direction of the Big Dipper changes with the seasons cannot be explained with the heliocentric model. Because in this model the direction of the earth's axis SN keep unchanged and points to the Polaris while it travels around the sun[4]. It is a common sense that when people observe the sky in the northern hemisphere, they always look north, as shown in Fig. 1(b). The only difference in observing the Big Dipper in different seasons is that their positions will slightly change, which can be ignored because the diameter of the earth's orbit is negligible compared to the distance between the earth and the Big Dipper. Therefore, the direction of the Big Dipper should be the same observed in different seasons with the heliocentric model.

As a matter of fact, the position and direction of the Big Dipper cannot change obviously in one year. The changes in its direction observed in different seasons are caused by the change of the direction of observation, which means that the direction of the earth's axis SN is changing. Is it possible that when the earth revolves around the sun, its axis SN rotates at the same time? If this is true, there will be no four seasons on earth, because the rotation of the earth's axis SN coincides with the earth's revolution around the sun. If the earth's north-south axis begins to rotate in spring, it will be spring all year round, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. If the earth's axis SN rotates with the earth's rotation, there will be no change in the four seasons. If the earth's north-south axis begins to rotate in spring, it will be spring all year round.

With the improvement of telescope technology, people have long found that the earth is not the center of the universe, nor is the sun. So, the movements of the planets, fixed stars, and all the stars are relative. For example, the rotation of the earth around the sun can be regarded as the rotation of the sun around its axis SS, as shown in Fig. 3(a). The earth located at point A, at time t_0 , moves to point B after time Δt , with an angular velocity ω , which is equivalent to that the earth remains stationary, and point C on the sun moves to point D with an angular velocity of negative ω and the same time Δt . From this point of view, the earth is “fixed” at point A. While the earth rotates, its axis SN rotates around the axis EE, as shown in Fig 3(b). On the other hand, the observer on the earth cannot feel the earth's revolution around the sun, which is different from the Geocentric theory and just because of the different references.

Figure 3. Take the earth as the coordinate origin O_e . (a) the revolution of the earth around the sun is equivalent to that the sun moves with same angular velocity in the opposite direction, and (b) while the earth rotates, its axis rotates around the axis EE.

This processing method is equivalent to coordinate transformation. It just changes the reference object of the earth's revolution around the sun, as if the center of earth is "fixed" at point O_e , and did not affect the rotation of the earth. So, sunrise and sunset are still caused by the earth's rotation around its axis SN. However, the axis SN is no longer fixed to pointing to the Polaris, but rotates around the axis EE, resulting in changes in the four seasons, as shown in Fig. 3(b). The northern hemisphere is perigee in summer and apogee in winter, which seems more reasonable than the heliocentric theory that summer is at apogee and winter is at perihelion. From this point of view, it shows that a rotating object will produce a force that repels other objects around it.

The directions of East, South, West and North are defined on earth. The direction of the star chart is marked according to the direction of the earth. The position and direction of the Ursa Major are relatively unchanged. So, their directions look changed just because the observation direction has changed with the changing of the earth's axis SN, but the observer is not aware of it, as shown in Fig.

4.

Figure 4. The directions of the Great and Little Bears are unchanged, which look changed just because the observation direction has changed.

For the planets in the solar system, from the inside out, the angular velocity of the planets becomes slower and slower, and the period becomes longer and longer. The periods of revolution of the eight planets in the solar system have been found on the Internet [5], and listed in Table 1. The angular velocity of each planet and its difference from the angular velocity of the earth are also listed in Table 1.

Table 1. The period of revolution, the angular velocity of each planet and its difference from the angular velocity of the earth.

Planet	Period of revolution	angular velocity(rad/day)	$\omega_p - \omega_e$ (rad/day)
Mercury	88 days	$2\pi/88=0.0713998$	0.0541856
Venus	224.7 days	$2\pi/224.7=0.0279626$	0.0107484
Earth	365 days	$2\pi/365=0.0172142$	0
Mars	687 days	$2\pi/687=0.0091458$	-0.0080684
Jupiter	11.9 years	$2\pi/11.9/365=0.0014466$	-0.0157676
Saturn	29.5 years	$2\pi/29.5/365=0.0005835$	-0.0166307
Uranus	84 years	$2\pi/84/365=0.0002049$	-0.0170093
Neptune	164.8 years	$2\pi/164.8/365=0.0001045$	-0.0171097

It is wonderful to observe the movements of planets with the earth as the origin of reference system. Because the earth is “fixed”, the revolution of the earth is replaced by the rotation of the sun. The angular velocity of the fixed earth is zero. The rotation speed of the inner planet gradually slows down

from inside to outside, while the rotation directions of the outer planets are opposite, and the rotation speed gradually increases. The rotation speed of the planets on the edge of the solar system is similar to that of the sun, as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. The movements of planets in the solar system observed with the earth as the origin of the coordinate.

It is actually observed that the sun rotates, and the planets move around the sun in different directions, only because of the change of the observation reference. It will also show that a rotating object will produce a force that repels other objects around it. The repulsive force between two objects is directly proportional to their relative rotational angular velocity.

In summary, in order to solve the problem that the heliocentric model cannot explain why the direction of a constellation changes with the seasons, a new reference system of observation is proposed. The observation results, in the new reference system, can not only explain the changes of sunrise, sunset and the four seasons, but also reasonably explain the changes in the directions of the Big Dipper with the four seasons.

References

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